

SEMANTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF PROVERBS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Annotation: This paper is aimed to analyse semantic features of some English and Uzbek proverbs. The results and examples of this paper can help to distinguish some differences in the meanings of the English and Uzbek proverbs and to learn some peculiarities of them.

Key words: Semantics, dialectical units, paremiologists, standard proverbial interpretation, literal/ figurative meaning.

Introduction. Semantics is a technical term for a specific field, a branch of language that studies meanings and contents. Since meaning is a part of language, semantics is considered a part of linguistics. However, meaning covers different areas of language. What aspects of the nature of meaning, that is, semantics, does it include? Or in what way should it be described? ...there is no general consensus on this issue yet. In general, it should be noted that the concept of semantics has been used in several senses since the past. And the use of the term semantics in sources with different content causes some confusion among the reader. Although many methodological approaches are aimed at clarifying this issue, there is still a lack of clarity regarding this term among linguists and representatives of other fields.

When semantics was introduced into linguistic discourse as a scientific term by Breal in 1883, its function was to describe the meaning of words and the change of meaning; however, this led to the use of the term in colloquial speech, sometimes semantics is often understood as a synonym for meaning. The semantics of proverbs is also understood as the meanings of proverbs. For example, Lundberg's 1958 work *The Semantics of Proverbs* focused on the meanings of proverbs and their contrasting interpretations across languages.

However, following the above tradition, semantics should be understood not in terms of meaning, but as the study of meaning or the science of meaning. Thus, semantics, in this sense, is not the object of study, but the science that studies the object; Since the object, here (i.e., proverb) is a linguistic expression, it requires the description and study (process of formation) of this meaning.

Proverbs are dialectical units in content and form, they differ from other language units in rhyme, sometimes polysemy, and richness of figurative meaning. It is precisely the metaphorical meaning of proverbs that has led to their study from a semantic point of view.

Literature review. Among the scientific works devoted to the semantic analysis of proverbs, the work of two important paremiologists Matti Kuusi and G. L. Premzhakov is incomparable. These two paremiologists created a universal system of proverbs. Kuusi studied the cultural concepts of proverbs, while Permzhakov paid attention to the symbolic, semiotic and logical aspects of proverbs.

The semantics of proverbs in English linguistics is discussed in P. Grzybek (Semiotic and Semantic Aspects of the Proverb), G.A. Lundberg (The Semantics of Proverbs), N.R. Norrick (How Proverbs Mean. Semantic studies in English proverbs). Grzybek argues that it is appropriate to take three semiotic dimensions: pragmatic, syntactic and semantic dimensions - as a starting point for analyzing the semiotics of proverbs. He also concludes that studying proverbs from the perspective of cultural semiotics can provide insight into various cultural mechanisms.

Norrick, in his How Proverbs Mean. Semantic studies in English proverbs, states that “the semantic properties of individual proverbs are interesting in themselves, and they can suggest an approach to the proverb. In addition, the standard semantic properties of proverbs can serve as examples of the main types of meaning relations that should be familiar to all members of a culture. The assumption that the standard meanings of proverbs are understandable to adult members of the language community serves as the basis for the use of proverbs in cognitive tests by psycholinguists and psychologists” and lists the following semantic properties of proverbs:

- 1) polysemy
- 2) pun
- 3) hyperbole
- 4) irony
- 5) tautology
- 6) paradox
- 7) connotation
- 8) imagery

We can see the semantic analysis of proverbs in Uzbek linguistics in the scientific works of J. Sh. Jumaboyava, O.P. Uralova, N. E. Abdullayeva, I. M. Mirzaliyev and several other linguists.

Analysis and results. In his collection How proverb means. Semantic Studies of English Proverbs, Norrick argued that proverbs, as linguistic units, have a standard

proverbial interpretation (SPI). This interpretation of proverbs is sometimes literal and sometimes figurative.

For example: **A flower cannot blossom without sunshine, a man cannot live without love**, the standard proverbial interpretation of the proverb is consistent with the literal meaning of the proverb. In this proverb, a person cannot live without love is compared to a flower not blooming without sunlight. We can also find similar examples in Uzbek: “**Qizlar gulni deydi, boy pulni**, or, **Har kishining didi boshqa har bir gulning hidi.**” However, sometimes the standard meaning of the proverb may not correspond to the literal meaning. We can take as an example the proverbs with the antonym **No roses without a thorn** in English and its equivalent in Uzbek, **Gul tikansiz bolmas**. These proverbs are used in the sense of "Every good thing has its downside, there is no pleasure without hardship" and acquire a figurative meaning.

For example, when translating the proverb "A man of words and not of deeds is like a garden full of weeds" into Uzbek, it means " **Ishlamasdan so'zlovchi odam o't bosgan bog'ga o'xshar.**" Through this proverb, we describe lazy but very talkative people who don't like work very much. But we cannot always use the Uzbek translation or meaning of an English proverb ready for the Uzbek language. As a very beautiful and alternative version of this, we can cite " **Ish bilsang tuzarsan, bilmasang buzarsan.**" In the Uzbek language, we can use the proverb " **Ish ishtaha ochar, dangasa ishdan qochar**" as an equivalent to this proverb. Let's consider the English proverb "**Head cook and bottlwasher**" as another proof of our opinion. The translation of the proverb in Uzbek is " **Ham bosh oshpaz, ham tovoq yuvuvchi**". The meaning of the proverb is that a person is engaged in several jobs, or is the owner of several professions at the same time.

At first glance, the proverb has an educational value and shows aspects encouraging to work. But the translation into Uzbek may not always preserve the original of the proverb. And we can't always use it actively both in spoken and written speech. The meaning of a proverb may not always come from the meaning of the words that make it up, but it is related to its figurativeness. Here, the strength of imagery in proverbs leads to the same interpretation of the same proverb in both languages. As the Uzbek equivalent of this proverb, which has been used since ancient times, we can quote " **Bir yigitga yetmish ikki hunar oz.**" Significantly, the proverb is still very active among both peoples today. We can use it not only in our daily life, but we can also see its beautiful presence in artistic works.

For example: "Yes, brother, master brother, with squeaky chrome boots on his feet and a woolen gymnastic coat worn by officers, rode a motorcycle and passed through the streets of Berlin. Yes!.. But, brother, it all happened behind the scenes. If there is no craft, where is such a beard and such honor? Yes, our fathers and grandfathers said: " **Bir yigitga yetmish ikki hunar oz**". The proverb in this passage

from the work " Bir yigitga yetmish ikki hunar oz" clearly and clearly describes to the reader that all Uzbek men and women are brave, brave, dexterous, businessmen and hardworking. The inclusion of this proverb in the list of English folk proverbs indicates that the English people are as hardworking as the Uzbek people. As we have mentioned, the characteristics of the admonition tone in the proverbs always show a person the right path and warn against bad consequences. For example: if we analyze the proverb "The laborer is worthy of his hire", it is an Uzbek alternative version: You have earned - soup, you have earned - stone. corresponds to the saying. The general meaning of the proverb in both languages is that what is achieved through hard work is always valuable, just like the sweet soup you are eating, but what is earned by easy means without hard work is impure and it is expressed that it will never be passed on to a person. In short, hard work deserves a paycheck.

Proverbs proceed to have affect on the listeners and coordinate them to require activities concurring to the message behind the sayings. The reason underlies the control of the maxims is that adages contain intelligence words depending on people’s involvement. They reflect social values and sensibility of the individuals. Maxims can be over counseled since of the reality they exist and still exceptionally crucial in our day-to- day encounter. A few of these maxims have been there from ancient era. They are born and still changed from one era to another. Proverbs can be considered as shared dialect within the family. Since sayings have uncommon affect between guardians and sons, e.g. guardians can inquire their children don't lie and tell the truth. Comparative to other shapes of convention, proverbs work as generic instrument individual cross examination in families. Parents may utilize maxims to coordinate their son's behaviors or considerations, but by consulting proverbs, the parental basic is expelled by one means or another from one individual to another. It could be an instrument to coordinate children in display by insinuating to mysterious past, particularly people conversation.

References:

1. Abdullaeva Nargiza Erkinovna. Ingliz va o‘zbek xalq maqollaridagi graduonimik munosabatlarning lingvopragmatik xususiyatlari. Filol. fan. fals. dok. (PhD).diss-Toshkent,2019.
2. Frantisek Cermak.Aspects of Proverbs: Lexical, semantic and pragmatic. Charles University in Prague, Karplinum Press.Page -46,2019.
3. Gotthardt H.H., Varga M.A. (ed.) Introduction to Paremiology: A Comprehensive Guide to Proverb Studies. – Warsaw/Berlin: De Gruyter Open, 2014. – P.21.

4. Grzybek P. Semiotic and Semantic Aspects of the Proverb. In: Gotthardt H.H., Varga M.A. (ed.) Introduction to Paremiology: A Comprehensive Guide to Proverb Studies. – Warsaw/Berlin: De Gruyter Open, 2014. – P. 94.
5. M. Mirzaliyev. Qadimiy turkiy maqollar semantikasi va stilistikasi. Filol. fan. fals. dok. (PhD).diss-Toshkent,2020.
6. Matti Kuusi” International Type- System of Provebs,G. L Premjakov “Избранные пословицы и поговорки народов Востока. - М., 1968. (Рец.: Харитонов М. С. Менделеевская таблица пословиц // Знание — сила От поговорки до сказки (Заметки по общей теории клише). — М., 1970 (в сер. «Исследования по фольклору и мифологии Востока (Проделки хитрецов. Мифы, сказки, басни и анекдоты о прославленных хитрецах, мудрецах и шутниках мирового фольклора . — М., 1972. Пословицы и поговорки народов Востока. Систематизированное собрание изречений двухсот народов. — М., 1979.
7. Neal R. Norrick. How proverb means. Semantic studies of English proverbs. Mouton Publishers Berlin · New York,Amsterdam,1985.-P.13.
8. Neal R. Norrick. Subject Area, Terminology, Proverb Definitions, Proverb Features. In: Gotthardt H.H., Varga M.A. (ed.) Introduction to Paremiology: A Comprehensive Guide to Proverb Studies. – Warsaw/Berlin: De Gruyter Open, 2014. – P.34.
9. Uralova O.P. Ingliz va o’zbek tillarida oila bosh leksemali maqollar semantikasi va strukturasi. Filol. fan. fals. dok. (PhD).diss- Samarqand, 2021.